

PREDICTION OF SURVIVABILITY OF LUNG CANCER PATIENTS USING DATA MINING TECHNIQUES - A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Data mining is the process of extracting useful information. Data mining is the main important step to reach the knowledge discovery. Normally for data preprocessing it goes through various process such as data cleaning, data transformation, data integration and data selection after these it is prepared for mining task. In data mining, one needs to primarily concentrate on cleaning the data so as to make it feasible for further processing. The process of cleaning the data is also called as feature elimination. In data mining, preprocessing plays a important role, since large amount of irrelevant information are present in the clinical data. In this paper, issues related with data cleaning, Data Conversion and Data Reduction processes are analyzed towards prediction of survivability of lung cancer patients in data mining. This paper also deals with the importance of preprocessing and attributes selection of dataset.

Keywords: Preprocessing, Data Cleaning, Data Reduction, DataConversion.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this survey, we collect the related information that demonstrates the importance of data mining in healthcare. As the amount of collected health data is increasing significantly every day, it is believed that a strong analysis tool that is capable of handling, analyzing large health data is essential. Analyzing the health dataset gathered by health survey using data mining techniques is very complex and is faced with very specific challenges, including privacy issues and data quality. In diagnosis of lung cancer prediction the data to be preprocessed is implemented [3]. This papers structured in four sections. Section-1 present Introduction and survey on related works. Section-2 present survey of preprocessing works. Section-3 presents the proposed algorithm. Section-4 present the performance analysis of the article has Conclusion and future directions of the work.

II. SURVEY OF RELATED WORKS

Padminin.P et al [6] presented data pre-processing technique necessary to perform data mining. Their work preprocess and composed the data. Data preprocessing on it and also they used classification algorithms. S.Nagaparameshwara Chary [12] provided an improvised technique for performing the data cleaning technique. That approach clean the data and remove the noisy and inconsistent data. Ankit Agrawal et al., [5] applied the data mining and knowledge discovery techniques to lung cancer dataset in order to display the details of preprocessing data. Their experiments provided an improvised technique for preprocessing the data. V.Krishnaiah et al.,[3] analyzed the data by using data preprocessing activities . The results showed the data cleaning techniques. Sathiya Priya.E [4] suggested that cleaning and discrimination to enhance the effectiveness of the mining process and also the major task is removing noisy and unrelated data to lessen the data volume for the reduce the complexity.

Table 1 shows the analysis of preprocessing with existing works:

S.no	Author	Function	Method	Issues Identified
1	P.Padmini	1.Composed and preprocessed manually	1.Manually preprocessed	No Efficient techniques for preprocess
2	Ankit Agarwal	1.Seer related preprocess 2.Problem related preprocess	1.Numeric to Nominal 2.Filtering the attributes	No Efficient techniques for data reduction
3	V.Krishnaiah	1.Data Cleaning 2.Data Transformation	1.Numeric to Nominal 2.Replace Missing Values	No Solution for attribute Selection
4	E.Sathiya Priya	1.Data Cleaning	1.Nominal to Numeric	No Discrimination Technique is applied
5	S.Naga Parameshwara Chary	1.Data Cleaning 2.Data Transformation	1.Replace Missing Values 2.Normalization	No Discrimination and attribute Selection is used

The following issues are identified based on this survey:

Issues in Preprocessing Techniques

- More memory space needed.
- Timing Complexity to build a model and searching
- Problem in identifying Distinct Factors.
- Problem in identifying which Instance is more needed.
- Problem in identifying unknown values.

Table 2 shows the machine learning based lung cancer prediction

S.no	Author	Core Work	Methodology	Issues Identified
1	N.V. Ramana Murty	Earlier warning to the users and to measure the performance analysis of the classification algorithms.	Classification, RBF Neural Network, Naïve Bayesian, DT, MLP, J48	Survivability rate is not considered.
2	P.Padmini	Prediction of lung cancer in the earlier stage using data mining techniques by considering the factors which has high probability.	Naive Bayes, J48	TNM staging is not analyzed.
3	V.Krishnaiah	Detection and correct diagnosis of the disease which will help the doctor in saving the life of the patient.	Decision tree, Bayesian classifiers and Neural networks	Categorical data is used for analysis where as Continuous data is not analyzed.
4	Ankit Agrawal	We analyze the lung cancer data available from the seer program with developing accurate survival prediction models for lung cancer.	IOS PRESS- Scientific Programming	Survivability rate is considered but is not accurate.
5	E. Sathiya Priya	Predict the lung cancer disease using two lung cancer datasets to improve the predictive accuracy of data mining algorithms.	International Journal of New Technology and Research (IJNTR)	Feature Selection is not Implemented.

In Table:2 Identified Issues based on this survey.The Issues Objectives are below:

Objectives

- ✓ Lung cancer prediction system can be further enhanced and expanded the survival rate of patients.
- ✓ TNM staging is analyzed.
- ✓ Categorical data and Continuous data are analyzed.
- ✓ Survival rate of Lung Cancer patients is accurate.
- ✓ Feature Selection is implemented.

III. PROPOSED WORK

In this methodology is used to predict survivability of the lung cancer patients. In the first phase patients data is collected and preprocessed along with replace missing values, Data conversion and feature extraction is done which sets off to the measured data and forms derived features that are intended to be informative and non-redundant. The extracted feature set is added to four different MLT and in the second phase analysis and prediction is performed. In the third phase comparison of J48, NB, SMO and Decision Table ML algorithms are done with their results and the one which provides the best predicted result is taken into consideration. The lung diseases can be predicted in the earlier stage by considering the other data mining techniques which helps in identification of clinical prognostic factors, allowing individualization of patient's treatment as well as improved quality of the tumor, the regional lymph nodes and metastasis which results in accurate stage of the lung cancer and predict the survivability of the patients. In below table have pseudo code for Replace missing values and Data conversion is used to preprocessing the lung cancer dataset. In this section algorithm for Cleaning, normalization and data reduction is proposed. The following data used the techniques for data pre-processing and data mining algorithms.

Figure 1: Architecture for Proposed Model

Preprocessing Algorithm Pseudo Code

Input: Lung cancer data with Noisy, Incomplete and Unwanted Details

Output: preprocessed Data

Begin

Convert NA entries by Replace missing values with max value of the instance.

Convert categorical data into nominal to binary values.

Delete unwanted details to reduce the space and time to build a model.

End

PRE-PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

The following data pre-processing techniques applied to the data before running the algorithm.

1. Replace Missing Values: This filter will scan all (or selected) nominal and numerical attributes and replace missing values with the modes and mean.

2. Discrimination: This filter is designed to *convert nominal attributes into numerical* ones; however the unsupervised version does not take class information into account when grouping instances together. There is always a risk that distinctions between the different instances in relation to the class can be wiped out when using such a filter.

3. Attribute Selection: The objective of my analysis (lung cancer prediction) did not require all the variables recorded hence there was need for data preparation, reduction and pre-processing. Data reduction is performed by selecting the most informative attributes in a dataset, while attempting to lose no critical information for classification.

Age	Gender	Alcohol	Pollution	Smoking	Dust	Genes	Diabetes	Fatigue	Chest	Blood	Wheezing	Swallowing	Weight	Yellow	Balar	Obese	Dry	Cc	Snori	T.St	N.Stag	M.Sta	Over	Histc	Timing	Deads	Survival
31	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	3	0	6	aden	457	1 SR-M		
27	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	2	aden	1095	1 SR-M		
35	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	3	0	6	squa	456	1 SR-M		
37	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	2	1	0	4	aden	941	1 SR-M		
46	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	5	aden	653	1 SR-M		
35	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	0	3	aden	1090	1 SR-M		
52	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	5	aden	737	1 SR-M			
28	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	5	large	577	1 SR-M		
35	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	2	2	0	5	squa	631	1 SR-M		
46	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	3	0	6	squa	912	1 SR-M	
44	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	squa	1515	1 SR-M		
64	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	2	0	5	squa	715	1 SR-M		
39	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	squa	1246	1 SR-M		
34	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	squa	1647	1 SR-M		
27	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	aden	1688	1 SR-M		
71	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	2	aden	1201	1 SR-M		
87	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	3	0	6	aden	420	1 SR-M		
34	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	4	aden	926	1 SR-M		
36	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	2	aden	1236	1 SR-M		
54	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	3	0	6	aden	439	1 SR-M		
37	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	3	3	0	6	aden	426	1 SR-M		
51	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	3	1	7	large	42	0 SR-L		
62	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	3	2	0	5	aden	745	1 SR-M		
39	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	2	aden	1541	1 SR-M		

Figure 2: Two Techniques are implemented - Replace missing values and discrimination

Smoking	Diabetes	Fatigue	BloodCoughing	Wheezing	SwallowingDifficulty	Overall.Stage	Timing	Deadstatus	Survivalrate
1	1	1	1	1	1	6	457	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	1	1	0	2	1095	1 SR-M	
0	1	1	0	0	0	6	456	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	4	941	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	5	653	1 SR-M	
1	1	0	0	0	0	3	1090	1 SR-M	
0	0	0	1	1	1	5	737	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	1	1	1	5	577	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	1	1	1	5	631	1 SR-M	
0	0	0	1	1	0	6	912	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1515	1 SR-M	
0	1	0	0	0	1	5	715	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	2	1246	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1647	1 SR-M	
1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1688	1 SR-M	
0	1	1	1	1	0	2	1201	1 SR-M	
1	0	0	1	1	0	6	420	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	4	926	1 SR-M	
0	1	1	0	1	0	2	1236	1 SR-M	
0	1	0	1	0	1	6	439	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	0	1	1	6	426	1 SR-M	
1	1	1	1	1	1	7	42	0 SR-L	
0	0	1	0	1	1	5	745	1 SR-M	
0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1541	1 SR-M	

Figure 3: Third Technique is Data Reduction - CFS BESTFIRST is used to select the highly correlated attributes and reduce the data.

In the above three techniques- data cleaning, data discrimination, data reduction we can predict preprocessed data for further process. Before preprocessing the available information in the lung cancer dataset is not suitable for further process. Hence the cleaning of data, categorical data and data reduction are necessary. After that only valid dataset to predict. These dataset will be used to identify the patient’s details clearly and to predict the patient’s survivability.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, performances of proposed algorithms are analysed using Prediction of Survivability of Lung Cancer Patients Dataset.

Figure 4: TPRATE and PRECISION –Before Cleaning

The fig. 1 shows the metrics with unwanted detail, which has to be cleaned with the help of data cleaning algorithm.

Figure 5: TPRATE and PRECISION–Before Cleaning

The above graph shows that after applying the data cleaning algorithm, the unwanted details have been removed and the selection of features. These preprocessed data will be used for prediction of further process of classification.

Figure 5: ACCURACY for Prediction

The accuracy analysis of Different Classification algorithms by to predict lung cancer patient's survival rate by using data mining techniques.

V. CONCLUSION

This review, investigated the data mining importance in many areas like medicine, education, E-commerce and website designing. These kind of work helps to provide consistent data for improving dataset and using data mining algorithms provide accuracy results for prediction. It has analyzed the significance of data mining phases such as preprocessing, data reduction and using the data mining algorithms for better performance. Also, it has described the various research issues and challenges. The importance of cleaning of data is also analysed.

VI. FUTURE WORK

In future use various Preprocessing Techniques and other Data Mining Techniques e.g., Time Series, Clustering and Association Rules used to get more accurate results for analysis and prediction. Another challenge is to integrate data mining and text mining. Another area would be to use Text Mining to mine the vast amount of unstructured data available in healthcare databases.

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